

MODELING AND OPTIMAL PLANNING OF SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEMS FOR RELIABLE POWER SUPPLY TO MEDICAL FACILITIES

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of modeling the optimal planning for the installation of an autonomous solar photovoltaic station for powering a vaccination room in a medical facility located in remote areas of the Sherabad district of Surkhandarya region, within the framework of the UNICEF project “Assessment of sites to determine energy needs and the state of infrastructure of 30 primary care clinics in Navoi, Kashkadarya, and Surkhandarya regions to develop plans for reliable electrification with a solar photovoltaic system”. The study examined the technical, economic, and environmental indicators of the system, taking into account the generating capacity of a 9 kW photovoltaic station at Family Clinic No. 85 in the Sherabad district of the Surkhandarya region. The PVsyst software was used to analyze the output indicators of the photovoltaic station. For the implementation of research in the PVsyst software, a database of basic climatic and actinometric indicators, such as outdoor air temperature, average and maximum daily air temperature amplitude, outdoor air humidity, wind characteristics, and daily sums of direct and diffuse solar radiation on a horizontal surface under average cloudiness conditions, among others, was studied and compiled for the period from 2005 to 2022 in the Surkhandarya region.*

As a result of the modeling, it was established that the annual electricity production of the autonomous PV station will amount to 12.31 MWh/year, which is sufficient to continuously supply electricity to the vaccination room, which consumes 19 kWh per day. Thus, the PV station can ensure reliable electricity supply to the vaccination room throughout the year.

Keywords: *autonomous photovoltaic station, PVsyst, modeling, solar radiation, climatic and actinometric data, continuous power supply, family clinic.*

Introduction. Economic growth in developing countries is closely linked to reliable energy supply, especially in remote areas where poverty is significantly dependent on the availability of energy services. As stated by many international organizations, such as the United Nations (UN) [1, 2], the World Bank [3], or the International Energy Agency (IEA) [4], electricity provides the necessary foundation for economic, social, and human progress, having a positive impact on industry, healthcare, education, climate change, food and water, security services, and communications. According to UN data, in 2022, about 750 million people worldwide did not have access to electricity, with more than 600 million of them living in developing countries. The World Bank also notes that access to electricity is one of the most important factors in reducing poverty. According to the bank's estimates, increasing access to electricity by 10% can lead to a

2.5% reduction in poverty levels [3]. In its report “World Energy Outlook 2022”, the IEA predicts that from 2022 to 2050, the demand for electricity in developing countries will increase by 2.5 times [5].

According to the authors [6, 7], the Republic of Uzbekistan has significant potential for the use of renewable energy sources (RES). The most promising types of renewable energy sources in the country are solar energy, wind energy, small and mountain rivers, geothermal energy, as well as the use of agricultural waste to produce combustible biogas.

Currently, the Government of the country is taking measures to develop renewable energy. According to data from the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a total of 78.0 billion *kWh* of electricity was produced in Uzbekistan in 2023. This figure represents an increase of 19 billion *kWh*, or 32.2%, compared to 2016. Additionally, it reflects a growth of 3.7 billion *kWh* (5%) compared to the previous year [8]. According to the strategy “Uzbekistan – 2030”, “...the basis for the transition to a green economy in the country will be an increase in the use of renewable energy. At the same time, it is expected to increase the capacity of power plants based on renewable energy sources to 40%.”

However, it is known that due to the low efficiency of photovoltaic panels (15-22%) and the low intensity of total solar radiation on a horizontal surface, achieving a certain power level requires a large installation space, which in turn leads to an increase in capital planning costs, design, and installation of solar photovoltaic systems [9,10].

According to the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics, in 2022, Surkhandarya region was the third largest in the country in terms of electricity consumption after Tashkent region (34.9%) and Samarkand region (22.8%) [11]. According to the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, today the average electricity consumption in Surkhandarya is 3.2 billion *kWh* per year [12].

According to the target indicators for the development of solar energy in the republic until 2030, a total of seven large projects for the construction of solar photovoltaic stations with a total capacity of 7000 *MW* are being implemented in the country. Of these, 2 solar power plants with a total capacity of 500 *MW* (Sherabad I - 200 *MW*, Sherabad II - 300 *MW*) are being built in the Sherabad district of Surkhandarya region. The solar power plant in the Sherabad district is planned to be put into operation this year. After the commissioning of these solar power plants, the share of electricity generated from renewable energy sources in the Surkhandarya region will increase from 1% to 15% [13].

Access to electricity is one of the essential conditions for ensuring the uninterrupted operation of refrigeration units where vaccines are stored. From 2019 to 2021, 67 million children worldwide missed their scheduled immunizations due to the pandemic, armed conflicts, declining trust in vaccines, and several other factors. In Europe and Central Asia, more than 931,000 children remained unvaccinated during this period [14-16]. Vaccination, from an organizational standpoint, represents a set of measures aimed at forming anti-infectious immunity by introducing vaccines into the human body, which are officially recommended or prescribed to prevent serious health threats to individuals and promote the sanitary and epidemiological well-being of the population. Given that the vaccination infrastructure in the Republic includes 1 national warehouse, 14 regional warehouses, 206 district warehouses, 3,138 vaccination points, and mobile teams, the study of issues related to the continuous supply of electrical energy is relevant [17].

As part of the technical assistance project "Assessment of sites to determine energy needs and the state of infrastructure for 30 primary care clinics in the Navoi, Kashkadarya, and Surkhandarya regions to develop electrification plans using solar photovoltaic systems," projects with standard solutions were developed for the electrification of 30 primary care clinics in the aforementioned regions using solar photovoltaic systems (PVS). These systems were designed to ensure reliable power supply to the facilities, where the main criteria were optimizing parameters considering the load of the facility and their uninterrupted power supply.

In this regard, based on the study of climatic data indicators of the Surkhandarya region and the power supply parameters of the clinic facility, the results of the development of project solutions for the installation of an autonomous PVS with optimized parameters for the continuous power supply of the vaccination room of the family clinic (FC) are presented. These results take into account the active and reactive power of devices and equipment. It should be noted that in medical institutions located far from the district center, uninterrupted power supply to refrigeration units in vaccination rooms is necessary to ensure the preservation of vaccines for their timely use.

Methods and materials.

During the research study, climatic and actinometric data from the region for the period 2000-2022 were utilized for statistical analysis, obtained from the data archive of the Sherabad meteorological station (Table 1).

Table 1

Information about weather stations located in Surkhandarya region

Weather station name	Location	Coordinates	Year of foundation
Sherabad	Sherabad district	37.800000, 66.083333	2000

Using modeling and simulation methods on the PVSyst software (v5.11), the output productivity of the PV station installed at the facility was forecasted, taking into account various factors such as climatic conditions, weather, consumer activity, energy losses, and others. The SunLocator application was used to simulate the position of the Sun at any time of the day, from sunrise to sunset throughout the seasons.

Data on the energy consumption of the selected facility, with the aim of identifying effective ways to improve energy savings, were calculated based on an energy consumption audit conducted through monitoring the data from the electricity meter installed at the facility.

The choice of the facility was justified according to the project's theme - a significantly remote region from the center of the Sherabad district in the Surkhandarya region was selected, located 61 km from the center [18].

Surkhandarya region is the southernmost region of Uzbekistan, located on the border with Tajikistan and Afghanistan ($38^{\circ}00'N$ $67^{\circ}30'E$) [18, 19]. The area of the region is $20,800 \text{ km}^2$. The climate of the region varies from dry desert in the south to subtropical in the north (in the Uzun area). The average January temperature is $+3^{\circ}\text{C}$, and July is $+30^{\circ}\text{C}$. In the plains, annual precipitation ranges from 130 mm to 360 mm , in the foothill areas - from 440 mm to 620 mm .

Surkhandarya region has three different climatic conditions, but BSk climates predominate according to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification (Table 2) [20].

Results and discussion.

Climatic and actinometric data (wind direction and speed, air humidity, minimum and maximum air temperature, atmospheric pressure, presence of precipitation, cloud level, amount of

incoming direct solar radiation, etc.) were obtained from the Sherabad weather station, located in the Surkhandarya region with a rather small time step - every half hour, which increases the level of data accuracy. Below are the main results obtained on the collection and processing of the main climatic and actinometric indicators of the Surkhandarya region [18, 21].

Table 2

Characteristics of the Surkhandarya region according to Köppen-Geiger

Classification	Index	Köppen Geiger	Regions
Cold semi-arid climates	19	BSk	Kumkurgan, Karluk, Bandikhan, Baysun, Dustlik
Hot summer Mediterranean climate	8	Csa	Denau, Uzun, Rabot, Kofrun, Pulgakim
Cold desert climates	4	BWk	Termez, Chegarachi, Gagarin, Kaftarkhan

Absolute minimum temperature -15.7°C , absolute maximum $+44.6^{\circ}\text{C}$, average maximum of the hottest month $+37.5^{\circ}\text{C}$, average maximum of the coldest month $+1.7^{\circ}\text{C}$, average annual temperature in the region is $+19,1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Maximum daily temperature range: in January $+18.7^{\circ}\text{C}$, in July 40.4°C . Outdoor air humidity: the hottest month – 54%, the coldest month – 24%. Wind characteristics in the region: monthly average in January – 2.3 m/s , monthly average in July – 2.1 m/s . The frequency of wind direction in January and July is more often observed in the eastern and north-eastern directions; the frequency of calm is almost minimal [22, 23].

Sunny and cloudy days are an important factor in determining the efficiency of photovoltaic plants, which convert sunlight into electricity. The number of sunny days determines the amount of sunlight that can be converted into electricity. Cloudy days block sunlight, leading to reduced electricity production from photovoltaic plants.

Based on a large-scale analysis of data obtained from the ground-based Sherabad meteorological station, the average daily sums of direct and diffuse solar radiation on a horizontal surface under average cloud conditions (Table 3), as well as the number of sunny (clear sky), partially cloudy, and cloudy days for 2000-2022, observed in the territory (Table 4) in the Surkhandarya region were identified.

Table 3

Daily average amounts of (direct/diffused) solar radiation on a horizontal surface under average cloudy conditions, MJ/(m² day)

Meteo Station	Average by month												Average
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	
SHER	11.16/	13.03/	16.31/	18.07/	25.2/	30.6/	30.42/	28.84/	27.11/	21.82/	15.01/	11.41/	20.77/
ABAD	3.85	4.86	6.55	8.6	8.28	7.49	7.13	6.52	5.54	4.72	3.82	3.31	5.9

As mentioned above, the technical potential of renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan is significantly higher, amounting to 270 million tons of oil equivalent (TOE), of which 265.1 million TOE is solar energy, which is more than three times the annual energy resource needs (Fig. 1) [12, 21].

Table 4

Average annual change in the number of sunny, partly cloudy and cloudy days in Surkhandarya region, 2000-2022.

Weather station name, ID	State of the sky	Number of days in months												Annual
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VI I	VI II	IX	X	XI	XI I	
Sherabod	Sunny	10	7	7	10	15	24	27	29	27	21	12	11	200
	Partly cloudy	6	7	8	9	8	5	3	2	2	6	7	7	70
	Cloudy	15	14	16	11	7	1	1	0	1	5	11	13	95

Fig. 1. Map from the series of natural potential of solar energy of Uzbekistan. to determine the amounts of total solar radiation incident on a horizontal surface (GHI).

As can be seen from Fig. 1, as well as according to the results obtained, in the territory of the Surkhandarya region, the average annual and average daily amount of GHI varies in the range of $1789 \div 1868 \text{ kW/m}^2$ and $4.89 \div 5.11 \text{ kW/m}^2$, respectively.

In fig. 2 shows the front view and a satellite image of the territory of FC No.85, which is located approximately 11 km from the center of the Sherabad district of the Surkhandarya region.

a

b

Fig.2. General view from the front (a) and satellite image of the territory (b) of FC No.85.

Results of calculating the energy consumption of the selected object.

Vaccination room of FC No.85 is equipped with the following electrical devices and equipment with the following power ratings (Tab. 5):

Table 5

Power indicators of the existing electrical equipment in the vaccination room of FC No.85 and their operating time.

No.	Electrical devices	Power (W)	Quantity	Total power (W)	Opening hours at fixed intervals				Σ t
					(0-6)	(6-12)	(12-18)	(18-24)	
1	LED commercial luminaires 15 W	15	2	30	0	6	6	0	12
2	Refrigerator Artel HD 276RN	219	1	219	6	6	6	6	24
3	Water heater 1500 W	1500	1	1500	0	2	2	0	4
4	Pharmaceutical refrigerator with ice jacket HAIER HBC-80	105	1	105	6	6	6	6	24
5	quartz lamp	30	1	30	0	0.5	0.5	0	1
6	Air conditioner ART-09HG	930	1	1200	0	2	2	0	4
	Total:	2799	7	3084	12	22.5	22.5	12	69

An audit of electricity meter readings over one year shows that the highest electricity consumption ranges from 60 kWh (in June) to 220 kWh (in April). According to calculations, the daily energy consumption of the vaccination room in the medical facility is 19 kWh. The peak load capacity per hour is 3.1 kW. The amount of energy that needs to be accumulated for 24 hours is 19 kWh. The power supplied to the PV system's backup device per hour (charging power) is 3.87 kW, and the system power required for the installation (PV system) is 9 kW.

The PVsyst software was used to analyze the indicators of the PV station being installed at the facility.

Fig. 3. Solar horizon in the selected region, according to PVsyst results

The horizon plot shown in Fig. 3 illustrates the availability of solar radiation. The red line represents the shadow around the solar field, while the blue line represents the automatic shadow from the photovoltaic modules. Fig. 4 shows the Sankey diagram for determining losses in the system.

Fig. 4. Diagram of losses of an autonomous photovoltaic system with a power of 9 kW.

The simulation results for installing a 9 kW PV system on the territory of FC No.85 in the Sherabad region indicate the need to install 18 PV panels with a power of 500 W each (dimensions:

2094x1038x35 mm, weight 24 kg) facing south at an angle of 36° to the horizon, with a distance of 2.20 m between the panels, and 7 batteries with a capacity of 200 Ah each (Fig. 5). The annual energy produced by the system will be 12.31 MWh/year (Fig. 4). In the above-mentioned system loss diagram, with an efficiency of 20.36%, the nominal battery energy under standard test conditions is 15.62 MWh/year. Due to system losses, the available output energy for the consumer decreases to 12.31 MWh/year, showing that system losses amount to approximately 21.2%. Given that the reduction in maximum PV module power by 0.3% - 0.5% occurs for each degree of operating temperature [24, 25], it can be estimated that temperature-related losses in the region will range from 6.6% to 8.3%.

Furthermore, based on preliminary and calculated data, work was carried out on the design of the system to be installed on the territory of FC No.85. Fig. 5 shows the diagram of the connection of the photovoltaic panels to the inverter, and from the inverter to the distribution board.

Fig. 5. Schematic diagram of connecting a solar photovoltaic system to an inverter on the territory of the FC No. 85 building.

As seen in Fig. 5, two arrays of photovoltaic panels (9 panels each) are connected to a 10 kW inverter through a combiner box (protective system), which in turn is connected to the grid, and simultaneously to the batteries (7 units of 200 Ah each). The grounding and surge protection system ensures the safe connection of the system to the grid and, in turn, provides the uninterrupted operation of the installed PV system.

In this case, the PV system is connected to the power supply grid of FC No. 85. During periods when the electricity production from the solar panels exceeds consumption, the excess electricity is fed into the grid once the batteries are fully charged. During periods when the electricity production from the solar panels is less than consumption, the missing electricity is drawn from the grid. In the absence of a grid connection, energy is drawn from the batteries.

Furthermore, Fig. 6 examines the energy production indicators of the installed PV system and the system's performance coefficient.

As seen in Fig. 6, the peak daily performance is 3.75 kW, which covers the peak energy demand of 3.1 kW per day. The power supplied to the batteries by the station per hour is 3.87 kW, and the system power required for the installation (PV system) is 9 kW, given the operating mode where the following appliances work in the vaccination room of the medical facility for 8 hours a

day: 30 W LED lamp, 1500 W water heater, HAIER AS12NB6HRA-B air conditioner, and for 24 hours a day, Artel HD 276RN refrigerator for vaccines (AC, 250 liters) 70 W, and Haier Icelined Refrigerator.

Fig. 6. Normalized production (per established kWh/kW/day) and productivity factor.

It is important to note that during periods of frequent cloudy days for more than two consecutive days, photovoltaic modules cannot provide the necessary 19 kWh of energy per day on subsequent days. To ensure uninterrupted power supply to the vaccination room, it is necessary to connect a backup power source. One option is a 3 kW diesel generator, as it can provide higher reliability, does not depend on sunlight, and can generate electricity at any time of the day.

Conclusion

The research results indicate that to ensure continuous power supply, it is necessary to accumulate 19 kWh per day to maintain the required conditions in the vaccination room of FC No. 85 in the Sherabad district of the Surkhandarya region. Considering the power load schedule of the facility and the reactive power of the equipment installed in the vaccination room, it has been identified that an autonomous photovoltaic system (PVS) with a capacity of 9 kW, a battery capacity of 1400 Ah, and a diesel generator (DG) with a capacity of 3 kW is required to provide autonomous power for two days in case of a power outage.

This setup can save 12.310 million UZS per year, based on the rate of 1000 UZS per kWh of electricity for legal entities (according to legislation). Additionally, according to our calculation methodology [26, 27, 28], the specific savings of natural gas and Angren coal amount to 1,583 Nm³ and 3.94 tons per year, respectively. The reduction in CO₂ emissions into the environment when burning natural gas is 2162 kg, and when burning Angren coal (depending on the carbon content in the coal) ranges from 15.2 to 21 tons per year, respectively.

This study was conducted for the vaccination room of one FC. Expanding the application of autonomous PV in the healthcare sector could not only improve the storage conditions of vaccines and medicines but also reduce primary energy resource costs for powering refrigeration units and other medical equipment in vaccination rooms by 50% or more, considering that the number of sunny days in the country is 280 days or more, depending on the region.

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